

National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

Transition to a permanently established NFDI

Position and perspectives of the DFG Executive Committee

Based on the report on the structural evaluation of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) published by the German Science and Humanities Council (Wissenschaftsrat, WR) last year, the Joint Science Conference (Gemeinsame Wissenschaftskonferenz, GWK) is currently preparing a new agreement between the federal government and the federal states. The aim of this agreement is to place the NFDI on a permanent footing. A decision is expected in summer 2026. In this context, the key question is which financial and organisational solutions are best suited to ensuring that the NFDI can continue to support researchers by providing needs-based research data management. The aim of this paper is firstly to contribute the DFG's extensive experience to the ongoing coordination process, gathered in particular through the review, evaluation and support of the NFDI consortia; secondly, it seeks to identify the key aspects to be taken into account in placing the NFDI on a permanent footing and in elaborating its future framework conditions.

The starting point for the discussions within the Joint Science Conference was the [report on the structural evaluation of the NFDI](#) published in July 2025. The recommendations put forward by the German Science and Humanities Council in this report include placing the NFDI on a permanent footing and establishing more centralised governance. The report also proposes promoting innovation and further development of the NFDI by means of project-based funding under an innovation programme administered by the DFG. Broadly speaking, these cornerstones are to be welcomed from the DFG's perspective; indeed they are essential to the continued development of the NFDI as a central information infrastructure for the German research system. In the further elaboration of the future of the NFDI as outlined in the Council's report, and particularly with regard to the transition process, the following points must be taken into account:

- ▶ Care must be taken to ensure that, even under a future governance structure that is likely to be more centralised, the NFDI retains its **community-driven and science-led character** so that discipline-specific needs can continue to be identified and addressed appropriately. The NFDI consortia have made a vital contribution to the success of the NFDI and constitute an essential basis for its further expansion and future success. For this reason, the integration of all consortia in the new target structure of a permanently established NFDI must be handled with particular care. The consolidation of existing consortia or their activities into a small number of disciplinary areas within the NFDI – or similar structures – may be appropriate, for example, but this should only be pursued where it creates genuine added value for the relevant communities and for the NFDI as a whole.
- ▶ The NFDI must ensure effective networking between actors, disciplines and structures in Germany. In doing so, it must address both those actors who have already made a significant contribution to the development of the NFDI through the consortia and those who do not currently belong to the NFDI. In order to achieve this, the German government, the federal states and other funding bodies should consistently align funding and financing structures with the NFDI so as to ensure the needs-based development of data infrastructures. At the same time, European and **international connectivity** must be strengthened and firmly embedded through the structures of the NFDI. Whether acting as a service operator or as a coordinator, the aim should be for the NFDI to serve as the clear German anchor point for both national and international matters relating to research data infrastructure and to play an active role in shaping standards across disciplines.

- ▶ In a permanently established NFDI, **external quality assurance** will remain indispensable. While permanent institutionalisation of the NFDI and thus a reliable flow of funding are essential, care must be taken in future – particularly in view of limited financial resources – to ensure that services and activities are funded and further developed only where they meet the specific needs of the relevant communities and of the German research system in general. To this end, in addition to developing transparent internal coordination and decision-making processes within the NFDI itself, robust, long-term external quality assurance mechanisms must be established that cover both quantitative and qualitative criteria. Clear and preferably quantifiable criteria must be defined for this purpose, along with potential financial consequences where targets are not met. This especially includes the establishment of mechanisms not only for admitting new actors to the NFDI but also for their withdrawal.
- ▶ The success of an NFDI placed on a permanent footing depends both on **the stability of the infrastructure** and on its dynamic further development, so there will be an ongoing need to balance these two objectives in a sustainable way. The reliable and collaboratively delivered operation of core services provides the indispensable foundation for the stability of an infrastructure with a distinctly national focus. This is particularly important given that the provision of high-quality core services with clearly defined service levels will build the trust required for intensive use on the part of researchers and research institutions. Dynamic further development also requires the continuous optimisation of interfaces with the research communities – regardless of their (current) involvement in the NFDI or its organisational structures.
- ▶ The stability and reliability of a permanently established and institutionalised NFDI are essential for the robustness of the system and should therefore be the primary focus in the short to medium term, but in addition it will be important to drive forward **needs-based further development**. An innovation programme administered by the DFG will be capable of fulfilling this role effectively, but it cannot serve as the sole driver of expansion and development. Rather, such a programme should be designed as a supplement to larger-scale, innovative or higher-risk projects and the integration of entirely new communities or emerging needs. At the same time, the science-led further development of services and structures within the NFDI as a whole must continue on an ongoing basis and form an integral part of its regular organisational processes. As far as the innovation programme is concerned, care must be taken to ensure that the topics funded correspond to needs within the NFDI; also, the results of funded projects must be integrated in the NFDI after project funding comes to an end and be further pursued, where appropriate with additional financial support.
- ▶ Rapid developments in the field of artificial intelligence, geopolitical tensions and significant dependencies on commercial actors have sharpened awareness of the need for strategic investment in a data infrastructure that is resilient, enables data sovereignty and is implemented at European level as far as possible. The extent to which this need is already recognised at the political level is reflected not least in the [High-Tech Agenda for Germany](#). As a central national anchor point for research data infrastructure, a future NFDI must therefore be **adequately funded**. The report by the German Science and Humanities Council does not specify concrete figures for future funding. Based on its own estimates, the DFG considers a total annual budget of at least €115 million to be necessary for the operation of infrastructure and services, as well as for further development and innovation. These estimates take into account factors such as inflation and rising personnel costs since 2019, as well as the expectation that the NFDI will increasingly assume responsibility for new tasks within a highly dynamic research and innovation system that were not foreseeable at the time of the current agreement between the German federal government and the federal states, or at least not to this extent.
- ▶ Based on a new agreement between the German federal government and the federal states from 2029 onwards, outstanding **legal issues** (such as the future legal constitution of the NFDI) must be carefully examined and clarified, particularly with regard to the financial administration and allocation of funds.

The above considerations demonstrate that further intensive conceptual work and in-depth reflection will be required to pave the way for a successful future NFDI capable of meeting the requirements of data sovereignty and resilience. From the DFG's perspective, it is therefore all the more important to establish without delay a competent transition team that involves representatives of all key stakeholders. This team should clearly define the individual steps towards a new target structure, thereby paving the way for the needs-based operation of research-related services. Only in this way can a smooth transition to a permanent footing be ensured.

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Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft e. V.

Kennedyallee 40 • 53175 Bonn, Germany

Postal address: 53170 Bonn, Germany

Tel.: +49 228 885-1

Fax: +49 228 885-2777

postmaster@dfg.de

www.dfg.de

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Contact persons at the DFG Head Office:

Dr. Johannes Fournier

Scientific Library Services and Information Systems

Tel. +49 228 885-2418

johannes.fournier@dfg.de

Dr. Lina Wedrich

Scientific Library Services and Information Systems

Tel. +49 228 885-2035

lina.wedrich@dfg.de

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